

Association between high serum Lipoprotein(a) concentration and renal pathology: Mechanisms of Lipoprotein(a)-mediated kidney injury

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Summary

Abstract: A high serum level of Lipoprotein(a) [Lp(a)] is inherited, but various chronic kidney diseases (CKD) can cause its secondary elevation because the kidney is involved in its catabolism. These two facts form the basis for the two theories of the causal relationship between high Lp(a) levels and CKD.

Purpose: This review aimed to summarize the complex relationships between Lp(a) levels and renal function, focusing on the molecular and cellular mechanisms. Furthermore, it aimed to differentiate between primary (genetically determined) and secondary (non-genetic) elevations of Lp(a) in various forms of CKD.

Materials and Methods: We conducted a comprehensive literature search across the following databases: PubMed, Science Direct, Google Scholar, and Wiley Online Library, covering the period from January 2010 to February 2025. The search strategy employed keywords such as “Lipoprotein(a)”, “chronic kidney disease”, “renal catabolism”, and “Lp(a) pathophysiology”. Inclusion criteria focused on peer-reviewed meta-analyses, cross-sectional studies with Mendelian randomization, and prospective clinical trials published in English. Studies with fewer than 50 participants or lacking clear markers of renal function were excluded. Data were synthesized through a thematic analysis of molecular mechanisms and a comparative review of clinical outcomes to ensure a robust overview of both genetic and secondary Lp(a) elevations. The research approach follows narrative literature review methodologies. The selection of studies focused on their relevance, the strength of their evidence, and temporal relevance.

Results: There is a complex feedback loop between high primary Lp(a) levels, CKD, and the secondary increase in Lp(a). Renal health influences Lp(a) levels, which in turn can further damage the kidney.

Key words: Apoprotein(a), Chronic kidney disease, Lipoprotein(a), Lysophosphatidic acid, Lysophospholipase D (Autotaxin), Phospholipase A2

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Introduction

Chronic kidney disease (CKD) is a global public health problem affecting 11% to 13% of the world's adult population (Deng et al. 2025). Based on the latest data from the Global Burden of Disease (GBD), many of the causes of CKD incidence and disability remain unknown (Deng et al. 2025). Research has shown that there is a risk of peripheral complications, including kidney complications, even when risk factors such as lifestyle, hyperglycemia, hypertension, and dyslipidemia are thoroughly controlled. That is why the search for biomarkers leading to kidney damage continues.

Some studies conducted in recent years define the role of Lp(a) as a direct factor contributing to the development of kidney disease (Xie et al. 2022; Liu et al. 2024). On the other hand, catabolic disturbances caused by CKD elevate lipoprotein levels. The need to unravel the causal relationship between the two is further intensified by their unfavorable impact on the cardiovascular system. According to the European Society of Cardiology (ESC), CKD and Lp(a) are two independent cardiovascular risk factors.

This review aimed to summarize the complex relationships between Lp(a) levels and renal function, considering the non-selective pathological effects of Lp(a) on the kidney - prothrombotic and antifibrinolytic effects, atherogenesis, inflammation, and oxidative stress, and their consequences. We emphasized the organ-specific cellular and molecular mechanisms of Lp(a)-mediated damage and their role in the development of various kidney diseases and summarized the association between elevated Lp(a) levels and the various forms of CKD.

Materials and methods

We conducted a comprehensive literature search across the following databases: PubMed, Science Direct, Google Scholar, and Wiley Online Library, covering the period from January 2010 to February 2025. The search strategy employed keywords such as "Lipoprotein(a)", "chronic kidney disease", "renal catabolism", and "Lp(a) pathophysiology". Inclusion criteria focused on peer-reviewed meta-analyses, cross-sectional studies with Mendelian randomization, and prospective clinical trials published in English. Studies with fewer than 50 participants or lacking clear markers of renal function were excluded. Data were synthesized through a thematic analysis of molecular mechanisms and a comparative review of clinical outcomes to ensure a robust overview of both genetic and secondary Lp(a) elevations. The research approach followed narrative literature review methodologies. The selection of studies focused on their relevance, the strength of their evidence, and temporal relevance.

Abbreviations

Apo(a)	apoprotein (a)
ATX	autotaxin
CCL1	C-C-chemokine ligand 1
CKD	chronic kidney disease
EC	endothelial cells
ESRD	end-stage renal disease

GEC	glomerular epithelial cells
GFB	glomerular filtration barrier
IL	interleukin
LPAG	LPA gene
LysoPA	lysophosphatidic acid
LysoPC	lysophosphatidyl choline
Lp(a)	Lipoprotein (a)
LPAR1	LPA receptors 1
Ma	macrophages
MC	Mesangial cells
MCP-1	monocyte chemoattractant protein 1
MI	inflammatory macrophages
Mo	monocytes
NK-c	natural killer cells
OxPIs	Oxidized Phospholipids
PAI-1	plasminogen activator inhibitor 1
PC	phosphatidylcholine
PI	phosphatidylinositol
IP3	inositol 3-phosphate
PLA2	phospholipase A2
PLC	phospholipase C
ROS	reactive oxygen species
SMC	smooth muscle cells
TNF-α	tumor necrosis factor- α
T-h	T helpers
TFPI-1	tissue factor pathway inhibitor 1

Lipoprotein (a) [Lp(a)]

Lp(a) was discovered in 1963 by geneticist Kare Berg. Examining human serum, he identified a unique antigen in the low-density lipoprotein (LDL-c) fraction. He named it apoprotein(a) [apo(a)]

It has been found that specific amounts of apo(a) can circulate freely, but in most cases, it is bound to the apoB molecule of LDL-cholesterol, which converts the latter into Lp(a). Upon further investigation, Berg found that a high serum concentration of Lp(a) was inherited. The LPA gene (LPAG) is located on the long arm of chromosome 6 (6q27) (Volgman et al. 2024). Codominant expression of the two LPA alleles determines the plasma level of Lp(a), which means that two of its isoforms can be found in each person (Sotiriou et al. 2006).

LPAG has been shown to have over 70% homology with the plasminogen synthesis gene (Farzam et al. 2025). It contains gene sequences similar to kringle IV and V of the plasminogen (PLG) gene, as well as sequences encoding an inactive protease domain at the C-terminus (Schmidt et al. 2016; Volgman et al. 2024). The distinctive feature of LPAG is that kringle IV-2 can have a variable number of copies, ranging from 3 to more than 40. The heterogeneity in the size of apo(a) is determined not only by the number of amino acids encoded in kringle IV-2 but also by the different degrees of their glycosylation. The concentration of smaller isoforms is higher (Reyes-Soffer et al. 2022). We can define apo(a) as a unique, hydrophobic, and highly glycosylated protein (Marcovina and Albers 2016).

The remaining part of Lp(a) consists of another protein, apoB, and a lipid core. Apo(a) and apoB are covalently linked to each other by a disulfide bond, with the binding site on the apo(a) side being kringle IV-9. The lipid nucleus is composed of cholesterol esters, triglycerides, phospholipids, and unesterified cholesterol on its surface. Lp(a) also contains other fat-soluble molecules, as well as sphingolipids of different numbers (Marcovina and Albers 2016). What makes Lp(a) more atherogenic than LDL-c is that it carries a large amount of oxidized phospholipids (OxPLs) - up to 90% of all OxPLs in the human body (Qin et al. 2024). Some of the OxPLs are covalently linked to two specific lysines from the kringle V domain of apo(a). The remaining OxPLs are non-covalently bound (extractable lipids) (Bochkov et al. 2010). Lp(a) is also a carrier for the enzymes autotaxin (ATX), which is associated with apo(a) and phospholipase A2 (PLA2), which is associated with apoB (Tsimikas et al. 2007) (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Lp(a) structure. Abbreviation: ATX-autotaxin; PLA2-phospholipase A2; b2GPI-b2 glycoprotein I; OxPLs-oxidized phospholipids. Adapted from Lampsas et al. (2023).

Role of the Kidneys in Lp(a) Catabolism

The plasma levels of Lp(a) depend on the balance between its synthesis and its catabolism. The rate of apo(a) synthesis in the liver primarily determines its concentration (Rader et al. 1994). The small apo(a) isoforms are synthesized more readily, and their serum concentration is higher. The main sites for Lp(a) catabolism are the liver and the kidneys (Jawi et al. 2020). The slow rate of catabolism does not significantly determine the organism's concentration in a normal state.

Back in the 1990s, when measuring Lp(a) in the ascending aorta and in the renal vein of patients undergoing coronary angiography, it was found that the venous concentration was lower by about 9% (Kronenberg et al. 1997). The relative difference in concentrations between arterial and venous blood is greater in patients with large apo(a) isoforms (Kronenberg et al. 1997) (Table 1).

This means that the kidneys take up atherogenic Lp(a) molecules. They express receptors with affinity for Lp(a) (LRP1 and megalin/LRP) that bind and remove the entire lipoprotein particle (Yeang et al. 2017). There is circumstantial evidence that the kidneys can dissociate the relationship between apo(a) and apoB and that the resulting free apo(a) and LDL-c can be catabolized separately (Jawi et al. 2020). Fragments of apo(a) are found in the urine of people who have low serum levels of Lp(a) (Yeang et al. 2017). Patients with kidney injury excrete significantly less apo(a) in their urine than healthy controls

Table 1. Arterial and venous plasma concentrations and absolute and relative concentration change of Lp(a) between the two vessels (Kronenberg et al. 1997).

Apo(a) phenotype group	n	Concentration		ΔConcentration		P<
		Arterial	Venous	Mg/dl	%	
11–22 K IV repeats	17	45.1 ± 23.6	42.3 ± 22.1	-2.8 ± 2.2	6.8	0.001
23–25 K IV repeats	23	21.0 ± 22.3	19.7 ± 21.0	-1.4 ± 1.7	6.4	0.001
26–40 K IV repeats	57	13.1 ± 14.5	12.0 ± 13.5	-1.1 ± 1.6	10.9	0.001
ALL apo(a) phenotypes		20.1 ± 21.6	18.7 ± 20.3	-1.4 ± 1.8	9.0	0.001

Data are given separately for three apo(a) phenotype groups defined by the number of K IV repeats of the smaller apo(a) isoform.

(Kostner et al. 1997). It was found that after the GFR (glomerular filtration rate) drops below 70 mL/min/1.73 m², the level of apo(a) in the urine decreases significantly, while at the same time, serum concentrations of Lp(a) and free apo(a) increase. This inverse correlation between renal function and Lp(a) levels persisted even after correction for albuminuria (Hopewell et al. 2018).

Lp(a)-Mediated Mechanisms of Kidney Injury

The mechanisms by which Lp(a) contributes to renal impairment are multifaceted. We can generally divide them into two: non-selective and selective.

Non-Selective Mechanisms of Renal Impairment Caused by High Lp(a) Levels

These include the prothrombotic and antifibrinolytic effects of Lp(a), atherogenesis, inflammation, and oxidative stress (Fig. 2).

Apo(a) is a structural analogue to plasminogen and competes with it for the same lysine-binding site on the fibrinogen/fibrin molecule, thereby inhibiting plasminogen activation and fibrin degradation (Greco et al. 2025). Smaller isoforms of apo(a) are associated with greater affinity of Lp(a) for fibrin (Lampas et al. 2023). Lp(a) increases the secretion of the plasminogen activator inhibitor-1 (PAI-1) and the tissue factor pathway inhibitor (TFPI-1), resulting in increased thrombosis (Greco et al. 2025).

Atherogenesis, Inflammation and Oxidative Stress

Lp(a) passes through the endothelial barrier of arteries and arterioles and is retained in the subendothelial space. Atherogenic and proinflammatory effects are manifested through three mechanisms: monocyte activation, endothelial dysfunction, and the proliferation and phenotypic transformation of smooth muscle cells.

Effect of Lp(a) on Monocytes

Through OxPLs, Lp(a) induces the secretion of monocyte chemoattractant protein 1 (MCP-1) (also called C-C chemokine ligand 2 (CCL2)) by endothelial cells. OxPLs retain their properties even after being taken up by macrophages, leading to accelerated apoptosis of these cells or their transformation into

Figure 2. Non-selective Lp(a)-mediated mechanisms of renal injury. Abbreviation: PAI-1 - plasminogen activator inhibitor 1; TFPI-1 - tissue factor pathway inhibitor 1; MCP-1 - monocyte chemoattractant protein 1; Mo - monocytes; Ma - macrophages; EC - endothelial cells; SMC - smooth muscle cells; MI - inflammatory macrophages; IL - interleukin; TNF-a - tumor necrosis factor-a; CCL1 - C chemokine ligand 1; T-h - T helpers; NK-c - natural killer cells. Prothrombotic and Antifibrinolytic Effects. Adapted from Qin et al. (2024).

inflammatory macrophages (M1). They release interleukin-1 β (IL-1 β), IL-8, and tumor necrosis factor-alpha (TNF- α) (Shapouri-Moghaddam et al. 2018).

Another important chemokine secreted by the endothelial cells after stimulation by apo(a) is C-C chemokine ligand 1 (CCL1) (Haque et al. 2000). Unlike MCP-1, in addition to monocytes, it also attracts other immune cells, including T-helper lymphocytes and natural killer cells (NK-c) (Qin et al. 2024). These cells express β 2 integrin Mac-1 on their surface. This adhesion molecule increases monocyte adhesion to endothelial cells and promotes their transendothelial migration (Sotiriou et al. 2006).

Effect of Lp(a) on Endothelial Cells

The effect of Lp(a) on endothelial cells includes the expression of adhesion molecules (VCAM-1, ICAM, and E-selectins), the secretion of inflammatory mediators (IL-8, IL-1 β , TNF- α , and IL-6), inhibition of the synthesis of desmogleins (proteins important for intercellular connections), and increased production of reactive oxygen species (ROS). This effect leads to endothelial dysfunction and increased endothelial permeability (Qin et al. 2024).

Lp(a) stimulates the proliferation and phenotypic transformation of SMCs (Qin et al. 2024).

The described non-specific mechanisms cause both macrovascular and microvascular kidney damage. The higher the concentration of Lp(a), the more OxPLs accumulate in the subendothelial space (Wilson et al. 2019). In macrovascular disease, atherosclerosis of the renal artery reduces blood flow to the kidney (Zhang et al. 2023). The consequences are ischemia, hypoxia, and ultimately nephrosclerosis (Hopewell et al. 2018). In microvascular damage, the glomerular capillaries are affected, which is why we define it as organ-specific.

Selective Lp(a)-mediated mechanisms of renal injury (Fig. 3)

Damage to glomerular capillaries.

Microcirculatory disturbances are a cause of glomerular sclerosis.

Effect on podocytes

There is still no proven direct effect of Lp(a) on podocytes. Lp(a) effects are indirect, through the inflammatory and immune reactions it induces, which subject the podocytes to oxidative stress. Free oxygen radicals contribute to podocyte apoptosis and necrosis. Thus, the glomerular filtration barrier is compromised (Nagata 2016). The final consequence of podocyte damage is glomerular sclerosis.

Effect on mesangial cells

The effects of Lp(a) on mesangial cells were demonstrated in vitro at the end of the last century by Mondorf et al. (1999). Lp(a) binds specifically to mesangial cells (HMCs) and, through the mediation of protein G, stimulates the activation of phospholipase C (PLC). Activated PLC breaks down phosphatidylinositol (PI), which is a major membrane phospholipid, into diacylglycerol (DAG) and inositol 3-phosphate (IP3). IP3 is a secondary messenger in the regulation of cell growth, differentiation, and intracellular Ca²⁺ accumulation.

This cascade leads to the activation and subsequent proliferation of mesangial cells, an increase in extracellular matrix, and glomerulosclerosis (Mondorf et al. 1999).

Figure 3. Selective Lp(a)-mediated mechanisms of kidney injury. Abbreviation: GEC - glomerular epithelial cells; GFB - glomerular filtration barrier; ROS - reactive oxygen species; PI - phosphatidylinositol; PLC - phospholipase C; PI3 - inositol 3-phosphate; MC - Mesangial cells; PC-phosphatidylcholine; LysoPC - lysophosphatidylcholine; LysoPA - lysophosphatidic acid; PLA2 - phospholipase A2; ATX - autotaxin; LPAR1 - LPA receptors 1. Adapted from Pinski and Norwood (2006).

The cascade constitutes a direct, receptor-mediated effect of Lp(a) on the glomerulus that extends beyond general vascular damage, a kidney-specific mechanism of injury.

Effect on tubular epithelial cells

In recent years, lysophosphatidic acid has been increasingly implicated in nephron damage. Lp(a) transports LysoPA and the enzymes that synthesize it, delivering them to the kidney's microenvironment (Fig. 4).

The enzyme phospholipase A2 (PLA2) is produced by macrophages involved in atherogenic plaques. It can bind to the apo B portion of low-density lipoproteins (LDL) and Lp(a) and form complexes (Lp-PLA2) that also enter the bloodstream (Colley et al. 2011). Smaller Lp(a) isoforms demonstrate increased PLA2 enzymatic activity relative to larger isoforms, indicating that apo(a) might modulate Lp-PLA2's association, despite lacking direct binding to the enzyme (Tsimikas et al. 2007).

The association and binding of OxPLs to Lp(a) may be part of the body's detoxification mechanisms. In this manner, OxPLs become accessible to the enzyme that degrades them, Lp-PLA2 (Tsimikas et al. 2007). The product of this reaction is the highly atherogenic lysophosphatidylcholine (LysoPC). At low concentrations, LysoPC binds to albumin, thereby neutralizing it (Tsimikas et al. 2007). When the concentration of LysoPC is high, it cannot be effectively taken up by albumin and subsequently becomes a substrate for the other Lp(a)-associated enzyme, ATX (autotaxin) (Bourgeois et al. 2020) (Fig. 1). Autotaxin (ATX) catalyzes the conversion of LysoPC to LysoPA. This bioactive lipid mediates inflammation, fibrosis, and cell movement (metastasis).

LysoPA performs its biological effects through six receptors (LPAR1-6) (Magkrioti et al. 2022). For renal damage, LPAR1 is the most important, as it is expressed mainly by epithelial cells in glomeruli and proximal tubules (Jin et al. 2021). Through it, LysoPA activates secretion of multiple chemokines by tubular epithelial cells (TECs), which drive chronic inflammation, cellular aging, fibrosis, and, eventually, progression to CKD (Magkrioti et al. 2022).

This model offers a new understanding of the relationship between dyslipidemia and renal pathology, shifting the focus from systemic effects to local, cell-specific events in the kidney. It has been proven that in kidney diseases, there is glomerular accumulation of Lp(a) and mesangial hypercellularity (Mondorf et al. 1999).

All the described mechanisms do not act independently but form a synergistic cascade that culminates in renal fibrosis.

Figure 4. Synthesis of LysoPA. Abbreviations: OxPLs – Oxidized Phospholipids, Lp-PLA2 - lipoprotein-phospholipase A2 complex; Lp-ATX - lipoprotein-autotaxin complex; LysoPA - lysophosphatidic acid.

Results

Association between high serum Lp(a) concentration and renal pathology:

- Patients with mildly reduced glomerular filtration rate, without CKD. There are studies that prove the inverse correlation between an increased level of Lp(a) and a slightly reduced eGFR (60–90 ml/min/1.73 m²). An extensive Chinese study, including 25,343 individuals with an average age of 50.7, found a relationship between the two indicators (Xie et al. 2022). The conducted multivariate logistic regression analysis showed that each 1-unit increase in log₁₀-Lp(a) (mg/dl) is associated with a 1.006-fold (95% CI 1.004–1.007, P < 0.001) increased risk of mildly reduced renal function. The conclusion from the analyses is that Lp(a) is a direct factor contributing to the development of kidney disease. A British prospective study (including 329,415 participants) of a cohort selected according to the same criteria assessed the risk of progression to CKD. It shows that elevated Lp(a) levels are associated with a significant increase in the risk of CKD (HR 1,32, 95% CI 1,19–1,46; P < .001) in individuals with slightly reduced eGFR and high-normal UACR values (10–30 mg/g) (Liu et al. 2024). The biological explanation for this link lies in the genetically determined high serum levels of Lp(a), due to small apo(a) isoforms, which induce renal damage through selective mechanisms: direct interaction with the receptors expressed by mesangial cells, or through the enzymes and bioactive molecules it carries, activating the pathological ATX-LysoPA-LPAR1 system.
- In patients with CKD. The thematic review series (Hopewell et al. 2018) summarizes the associations of CKD and dialysis modalities on Lp(a) levels (Table 2).
- In patients without nephrotic syndrome who have large apo(a) isoforms and proven renal impairment, Lp(a) levels increase with disease progression. The concentration is highest in end-stage renal disease (ESRD) (Hopewell et al. 2018). Lp(a) concentrations are five to ten times higher in people undergoing routine hemodialysis compared to those in the early stages of CKD (Hopewell et al. 2018). The concentration of serum Lp(a) reduces after kidney transplantation among individuals with large apo(a) isoforms (Kronenberg et al. 1996). In patients with small apo(a) isoforms, the Lp(a) concentration does not change significantly during the same stages of disease progression (Hopewell et al. 2018). These facts support the claim for the secondary (non-genetic) lipoprotein anomaly (Kronenberg et al. 1996). The reason is impaired catabolism due to renal tissue loss, rather than increased synthesis. The specific thing is that this is observed only in the subgroup of patients with large apo(a) isoforms, i.e., in them, the renal clearance pathway is probably more important and affects the Lp(a) particles more selectively.
- In individuals with nephrotic syndrome, elevated Lp(a) concentrations are observed, irrespective of apo(a) isoform size (Hopewell et al. 2018). Therapeutic reduction of proteinuria leads to a corresponding decrease in serum Lp(a) concentration. The underlying cause is enhanced hepatic synthesis, which occurs in response to increased urinary protein loss.

- The Lp(a) concentration is higher in patients undergoing peritoneal dialysis, independent of the apo(a) isoform size (Hopewell et al. 2018). Again, the underlying cause is enhanced hepatic synthesis.
- In hemodialysis, protein losses are insignificant, and Lp(a) elevates only in patients possessing large apo(a) isoforms. The cause is impaired renal catabolism.

Table 2. Summary of the effects of CKD and its treatment on Lp(a) levels (Hopewell et al. 2018).

Kidney disease	GFR (ml/min/1.73 m ²)	Description	Estimated global prevalence	Plasma Lp(a) levels (relative to controls)
CKD KDIGO Stage				
G1	≥90	Kidney damage with normal function (+persistent albuminuria)	3.5%	+
G2	60–89	Mild decrease in kidney function (+persistent albuminuria)	3.9%	++
G3	30–59	Moderate decrease in kidney function	7.6%	++/+++
G4	15–29	Severe decrease in kidney function	0.4%	++/+++
G5	<15	Kidney failure/end-stage renal disease	0.1%	++++
G5D (HD)	n/a	End-stage renal disease treated by haemodialysis	<0.1%	++
G5D (PD)	n/a	End-stage renal disease treated by peritoneal dialysis	<0.1%	+++
Nephrotic syndrome	Any	Protein-losing state	Often transient	++++
Kidney transplant	Any	CKD patients after renal transplantation	<0.1%	as per GFR

Conclusion

Lipoprotein(a) is a complex and multifaceted risk factor whose role in renal damage is still being further elucidated. The apo(a) isoform size-dependent increase of Lp(a) is a result of different underlying mechanisms (Fig. 5).

Ideally, laboratory analysis should provide information on the number of lipoprotein particles and their size. We can obtain such results using nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectrometry. This analysis is expensive, requires specialized equipment, and has not yet entered widespread practice. With routine standardized methods, we currently measure the number of Lp(a) particles. Population screening to determine baseline Lp(a) levels for every individual, combined with an understanding of Lp(a)-mediated renal injury mechanisms, will assist us in interpreting laboratory results. This approach is beneficial for both prevention and guiding therapeutic choices (the latter, subject to ongoing clinical trials) in established renal disease. Conventional lipid-lowering therapies, such as statins, have a limited impact on Lp(a) levels. Emerging RNA-based therapies offer promising results for patients with CKD. In clinical trials, medications such as antisense oligonucleotides (e.g., pelacarsen) and small interfering RNA (siRNA) molecules (e.g., olpasiran and lepodisiran) are being studied. Their target is the suppression of hepatic LPA gene expression. The reduction of the concentration of Lp(a) after their application is over 80%. In patients with impaired renal catabolism, these interventions can mitigate the secondary rise of Lp(a) and slow down the progression of renal fibrosis.

Figure 5. Lp(a)-mediated mechanisms of kidney injury. Abbreviations: LPAG-LPA gene; CKD-chronic kidney disease; ESRD-end-stage renal disease.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Use of AI

No use of AI was reported.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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